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Innovative Educational Activity of a Teacher as a Result of Working with Gifted Children

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of innovative educational activities of teachers as a result of working with gifted students. The national goal of the Russia until 2030 states that it is necessary to create all conditions for self-realization and disclosure of the talent of each student. It is necessary to keep in mind the fact that many students do not have possible potential (hidden) giftedness due to the lack of a built-up system for ensuring the effectiveness of working with gifted students to reveal the talent of each of them. The article focuses on identifying the "innovativeness" of teachers, on determining the possession of an emotional and evaluative attitude to innovations, as well as on innovative competence, which ensures the effectiveness of using the latest technologies while working with gifted students. The following research methods were used: analysis of special (psychological and pedagogical) literature; survey; observation. The research involved 50 teachers who took advanced training courses "Psychological and pedagogical technologies for working with gifted children". To identify the readiness of teachers for innovative pedagogical (educational) activities, a questionnaire consisting of 6 blocks was conducted.

According to the results of the survey, the readiness (full and partial) of teachers working successfully with gifted students – participants of the survey for innovative pedagogical activities was established.

Keyword: innovative educational activity, teacher, gifted student, readiness component, extensive innovation, intensive innovation.

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Introduction

The issue of giftedness is emphasized as a national goal of the country's development until 2030 by the decree of the President of the Russian Federation V.V. Putin, which states about the need to create all conditions for self-realization and for the disclosure of the talent of each student (Decree on the National Development Goals of Russia until 2030, 2020).

It is necessary to bear in mind the fact that many students did not have a possible potential (hidden) giftedness due to the lack of a well-built system of supplying the effectiveness of work with gifted students to reveal the gift of each of them. Therefore, today it becomes relevant to consider the mastery of the necessary competencies by teachers, which will be acquired as a result of innovative educational activities while working with gifted students. In this case, the teacher's innovative educational activity will be the result of purposeful interaction between the teacher and gifted students, leading to the disclosure of the potential of each gifted student. Improving the competencies of teachers in organizing work with gifted students is possible if they wish to master effective innovative technologies for interacting with gifted students.

It should be recalled that in the study we used “extensive” innovations, which imply the attraction of new opportunities for increasing the quantitative characteristics of the pedagogical product mainly due to new information technologies, redistributing time for various types of educational activities, integration and personalized work with gifted students. They also took into account “intensive” innovations - innovations that provided for development through innovative internal reserves, leading to the improvement of teachers' competencies in organizing work with gifted students, thanks to which a unified approach to the concept of “giftedness” would be built and innovative technologies for working with the gifted would be mastered students.

Innovative educational activity of the teacher will be the result of working with gifted students, so it is essential to improve the competence of teachers in the organization of work with gifted students; to master effective innovative technologies while working with gifted students.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to identify "innovativeness", i.e., possession of an emotional and evaluative attitude to innovations, as well as innovative competence, which in turn ensures the effectiveness of using the latest technologies while working with gifted students. It should be noted that determining the continuous updating of the capabilities of teachers working with gifted students is a primary goal in the life cycle of innovation, because innovations lose their novelty over time, and the finish line comes. (какая финишная прямая? Перефразируйте нейтрально)

Literature review

Given the fact that there is an undetected possible giftedness in many students, which is quite difficult to establish during diagnostics, it is necessary to build a system for supplying the effectiveness of work with gifted students to reveal the gift of each of them, which provides for the mastering of the necessary competencies by teachers acquired as a result of innovative educational activities (Bogoyavlenskaya & Bogoyavlenskaya, 2018; Gabdulkhakov, 2018; Khalikova, 2020).

Fedorov, Ilaltdinova, Frolova, Kisova and Arifulina wrote that the level of professional skill of a teacher in working with students directly depends on his or her ability to teach and the stability of professional motivation (2019). In this regard, the authors of the current research designate a special place for a teacher who has professional motivation to work with gifted students, participates in innovative activities, finds the right solution in different pedagogical situations.

Ushinsky (2017) points out that there is no doubt that much depends on the general routine in the institution, but the most important thing will always depend on the personality of the direct educator, standing face to face with the pupil: the influence of the personality of the educator on the young soul is that educational force that cannot be replaced by a textbook, nor moral maxims, nor a system of rewards and punishments. Undoubtedly, the personality of the teacher as an educator plays a very important role in working with students who are brought up on the example of their teachers, therefore, thanks to innovative activities, the teacher is constantly improving, becoming an example for his students.

According to Andreev (2012) each person remembering teachers at school, most often recreates in memory, first of all, not only the professional qualities of a teacher, but also a teacher as a complete personality. Skulsky (1986) writes that the professional and personal qualities of a teacher, the features of his or her professional activity with the nature of the activities of students and their personal qualities are very closely interrelated and mutually conditioned.

Lizinsky (2012) proposed his own scale of measurement for assessing the professionalism of a teacher, noting the success factor. Any boring activity can be turned into a game, using game techniques in the classroom, so that children learn with desire (Gurin, 2010). Khalikova (2019) considers the educational game in the classroom as means of activating the cognitive activity of students, to motivate the educational process.

In their works, Olkhovskaya (2011) and Akhmerova (2010) write about the professional education of teachers, about the theory and methods of teaching, focusing on the productive professional activity and the health of teachers, on the problems of preserving the health of teachers and their students, pointing to the need to prevent diseases associated with the peculiarities of the professional activity of teachers.

Golovner (2019), considering and analyzing the competition "Teacher of the Year of Russia-2019", writes whether a teacher is needed to spread an e-school, if the main goal of the competition is to identify talented teachers who can serve as beacons for their profession, to popularize it. Also, will there be a contradiction between the tendency to unite and replicate innovative pedagogical experience developing in the educational space. Lemov (2014) and Dirksen (2013) believe that the success of experienced teachers is based on everyday hard work, so it is important to focus on the correct creation of learning conditions and the selection of the necessary information.

In the vast majority of modern theories, the desire to understand giftedness is a common thread. Any program of work with gifted students, without a theoretical basis, will be just a haphazard set of individual views, methods and techniques that do not always correspond to the goals set. Conceptual models in educational institutions makes it possible to structure programs for the diagnosis, education and training of gifted students, to organize coordinated work in all areas and stages, and to explain the essence and details of the program to teachers and parents of gifted students.

This was written by Morozova and Grigorieva (2007) in their textbook, where positions of foreign and domestic scientists on methodological problems of the development of giftedness at various age stages were presented. We can consider two modern views: the Russian view of Shcheblanova (2011), about how difficult it is to be talented and about the gifted children who remain undeveloped due to various problems and reasons, who need help to discover their talents; the foreign view of Jose (2012), about the formation of talent, given that most children have some "basic" talent (strength), so it is necessary to create such conditions that gifted children can develop their "basic" talent with the help of parents and teachers from an early age.

To train gifted students, gifted teachers are needed; such teachers are trained in specialized educational institutions. Not all students of pedagogical specialties in the future become teachers, moreover, gifted teachers who devote their lives to teaching students. It is very important to rethink the professional training of future teachers, not only because they educate the future generation, but also so that they are role models. Gifted students have academic and emotional skills, and through effective gifted education, they are encouraged to think creatively and critically. Teachers working with such students will also have key design principles, mastering a person-centeredness, the ability to act, the nature of cooperation and attentiveness to the process, to the situation. In this case, they will present themselves as powerful resources for example to gifted learners, future teachers will follow the example of this teacher (Spoon, Rubenstein, Shively, Stith, Ascolani & Potts, 2020).

For the training of the gifted and talented, programs are drawn up based on research practice, according to state policies, for which general education institutions are responsible. This policy should respond to the academic demands of gifted learners, and provide an opportunity for the development of the learner's giftedness. For the analysis, several innovative plans for teaching gifted students were investigated, which advised the inclusion of recommendations for recognizing giftedness, options for serving gifted children (Lockhart & Meyer & Crutchfield, 2021).

For gifted students, different programs are used that are designed for their development. Developing innovative programs reveal the potential of gifted students to the maximum, since these programs take into account an individual approach to each gifted student. When drawing up such programs, they attach importance to the characteristics of each gifted student, identifying the inclinations and abilities, since they are available in every gifted person. The task of the teacher is the development of natural abilities and the disclosure of the properties of the child, so that he achieves his mission. Using innovative approaches, new forms of communication with such an extraordinary student, a talented teacher has the opportunity to maximize the potential of this student. In this case, the style of the student coincides with the style of the teacher, this is the case when the fate of both a talented teacher and a gifted student will be successful. Unfortunately, not all educators manage to "find" the key to such extraordinary students (Cavilla, 2019).

Teachers who are involved in innovative activities as a result of working with gifted students, after a certain time, become high-class specialists in this field. It is the involvement in innovative activities that inspires teachers to take new actions, to new discoveries when working with gifted students. Such teachers become a source for adopting an innovative experience when colleagues take a positive example from her. To do this, the teacher must have free time for creativity, to work on self-improvement, self-development (Cornejo-Araya & Kronborg, 2021).

The review of the literature showed that despite the large number of publications on the educational activities of teachers, on the giftedness and gifted students, there are no articles devoted to innovative educational activities of teachers as a result of working with gifted students. In modern conditions, in conditions of a high-tech society, in conditions of the challenge of the time, we need highly qualified, successful, effective teaching staff who are able to identify, motivate, accompany and predict the professional development of gifted young people. It is with such a need that it is possible to form innovative educational activities of the teacher, which will be a consequence and reflection of work with gifted students.

Methodology

Research methods: theoretical methods-analysis of special (psychological and pedagogical) literature; empirical methods - questionnaires; observation. The research involved 50 teachers who took advanced training courses "Psychological and pedagogical technologies for working with gifted children", a questionnaire was implemented on the readiness of teachers for innovative pedagogical (educational) activities. The survey was conducted to identify the readiness for innovative pedagogical activity with the use of innovative means of achieving the pedagogical goal, as well as to detect teachers' motivational and value relations to innovative pedagogical activity.

Every teacher has to deal with extraordinary students who require a special non-standard approach to communication and learning. Therefore, the special importance of the work of the school teacher, who has the desire to work with such students, is to identify early and correctly those who are striving for deep knowledge of various fields of science. To provide professional support and the necessary assistance in developing abilities of gifted students, the teacher must continuously work on himself or herself, be an initiator in the co-creation of "himself" or "herself", be involved in innovative educational activities (Khalikova, 2018; Khalikova, & Sharifullina, 2019).

Today, to identify the nature of giftedness, new diagnostic methods are required, since the well-known psychometric tests and tests for identifying intellectual giftedness lose their reliability in relation to the special structure of giftedness and the mediocrity of the mental and intellectual resources of a gifted student. The most modern and reliable form of identification of giftedness or signs of giftedness is considered to be monitoring, accompanied by longitudinal observations that meet specific requirements:

- the complex nature of the study of various aspects of the behavior and occupation of a gifted student;
- the duration of the process of identifying and identifying signs of giftedness in different situations;
- analysis of the behavior of a gifted student in the profile area.
- expert evaluation of the product of the class or activity of a gifted student;
- taking into account the zone of immediate development, the forecast and development of a personalized individual educational trajectory of a gifted student;

- multiple and multi-stage research, gifted student;
- based on the analysis of the products of joint activities, longitudinal observations, conversations, expert assessments of parents and teachers.

On the basis of these requirements, the innovative activity of teachers was diagnosed, and the professional readiness to implement innovative activities was determined. Teachers were asked questions, the answers to which allowed to determine the readiness of teachers to implement innovative activities, choosing the answer "yes "(+)" or " no " (-) they expressed their opinion.

The survey consisted of 6 blocks (modules): the cognitive component of readiness (knowledge in the field of pedagogical innovation was taken into account); the motivational component of readiness; the activity component of readiness (experience in innovative work); the creative component of readiness (creativity); the technological component of readiness; readiness to reflect on professional activities. The maximum score for the questionnaire is 49 points, the level of readiness is determined by the number of points: 43-49-indicates full readiness; 42-31-partial readiness; 30-0- lack of preparation for the implementation of innovative educational activities.

Based on the conducted research, it can be concluded that in the study we used extensive innovations, attracting the latest means to increase the quantitative characteristics of the pedagogical product mainly due to new information technologies, the redistribution of time for various types of educational activities, integration and personalized work with gifted students.

There were also intensive innovations-innovations that provided for the development of innovative internal reserves, leading to the improvement of the competence of teachers in the organization of work with gifted students, thanks to which a unified approach to the concept of "giftedness" was built; innovative technologies for working with gifted students were mastered. Among the teachers participating in the survey, 89% were found to be fully prepared and partially prepared for innovative teaching activities.

Results

Recall that the study was conducted among teachers who work in traditional and innovative educational structures. The traditional education system is characterized by relatively stable functioning, as a rule, the relationship between the teacher and students is built as a subject-object, where the teacher is in limited conditions and his or her activities are controlled by specific requirements. Innovative educational structures work in search mode, aimed at continuous updating of education, in these conditions, modernization becomes the mechanism of its continuous development. The essence of innovative processes in education is the development of pedagogical conditions for ensuring continuous innovation movement.

The success of the development of innovative education is determined precisely by the readiness of successful teachers to work in an innovative mode, to work continuously, which is expressed in a flexible, prompt response of their teaching activities to the constantly updated information environment, the constantly changing needs of the individual, the labor market, and society. Sustainability, stability of the development of innovations in education is achieved thanks to the professional competence of the teacher.

The most important factor in the innovative development of education is the purposeful development of the professional competence of teachers in the conditions of continuous work with them in innovative educational structures for special training-teachers who are competent in the field of pedagogical innovations.

When creating an innovative educational environment in educational structures, successful teachers are involved in innovative activities, in which the professional competence of teachers will be purposefully developed, the introduction of innovations in the innovative educational process will lead to various positive changes – to new teaching methods and technologies.

We studied the innovative educational activities of teachers of traditional and innovative schools when working with gifted students according to the criteria-indicators – continuing education; exchange of experience; becoming an expert; becoming a mentor; mutually conditioned results.

Note that any innovation, any novelty – innovation initially on the part of teachers working in traditional schools, causes resistance due to the fact that many of them do not have the desire to change anything in the course of their professional activities. The reasons that prevent the introduction of innovations in pedagogical activity are explained by the lack of goals in life and interest in self-improvement and self-development, the dominance of motivation to avoid high-quality educational results, unformed pedagogical communication skills, emotionally unbalanced, fear of risk.

Teachers who work in innovative schools are motivated to implement innovations in their teaching activities, have a conscious goal in life, are active, flexible in their work, have formed skills of pedagogical communication, are emotionally balanced, and are constantly ready for risk.

The environment of an innovative educational institution has a significant impact on the development of the "innovativeness" of a teacher, his or her professional competence. It can be said that teachers working in innovative schools have pedagogical giftedness that precedes the development of new areas of intellectual giftedness in their students.

Thanks to the level of methodological skill, the planned mutually conditioned pedagogical co-creation of a "successful" teacher with students, his or her activity is predetermined, which will be the result of influencing the formation of the desired personality qualities of a gifted student, for further progress in training, development and education.

In the course of the study, taking into account the criteria-indicators of continuous work with successful teachers, all the planned next actions were carried out by teachers working in traditional and innovative schools.

It was mentioned above that during our research, various methods were used, including pedagogical observation of innovative activities of teachers (lessons, extracurricular activities, interaction with gifted students, etc.). Pedagogical observation was supplemented with developing conversations with students and with students who studied and passed pedagogical practice with the studied teachers, in order to identify the professional and personal qualities of a successful teacher working with gifted youth.

It should be noted that during this period, gifted students became prize-winners and winners of Olympiads, competitions, tournaments of various levels; the average score of passing the state final exam by students increased; students-future teachers showed high results in their studies, participated and won at student conferences.

Within the framework of the study, individual (personal and professional) conversations on the concepts of "giftedness" were conducted with teachers (traditional and innovative schools) at advanced training courses. The authors offer options for the answers of teachers who participated in the conversations and answered the question "do you think a gifted student is" (a student with unique learning abilities; a creative student, a student with extraordinary thinking; a genetically embedded mind and the ability to acquire everything; who knows more than others and thinks differently; a student who requires a lot of attention; special child, a step above the rest; student, who develops in all directions; has internal preconditions for high achievement; student, a very developed either in one area or in several; student who thinks faster than others, or penetrates deeper than other children, etc.).

The last stage was the analysis of the eligibility categories "success" to the teachers working in traditional and innovative schools, through static analysis (in percentage).

As can be seen from the analysis (table), teachers working in innovative schools show excellent results, the defining criterion-indicator (mutually conditioned results) - 100%, which means "innovativeness" of the teacher. Although 90% of teachers working in traditional schools participate in continuing education, according to the defining criterion (mutually dependent results), the figure is low – 52%.

Table 1. Continuous work with successful teachers.

Teachers Criteria-indicators working	in traditional schools	in innovative schools
continuing education,%	90	100
exchange of experience,%	78	100
becoming an expert,%	59	97
becoming a mentor,%	53	95
mutually dependent results,%	52	100

Discussion

Teachers working in innovative schools are motivated to implement innovations in their teaching activities, have a conscious goal in life, are active, flexible in their work, have formed skills of pedagogical communication, are emotionally balanced, and are constantly ready for risk.

The environment of an innovative educational institution has a significant impact on the development of the "innovativeness" of a teacher, his or her professional competence.

It can be said that teachers working in innovative schools have pedagogical giftedness that precedes the development of new areas of intellectual giftedness in their students.

Thanks to the level of methodological skill, the planned mutually conditioned pedagogical co-creation of a "successful" teacher with students, his or her activity is predetermined, which will be the result of influencing the formation of the desired personality qualities of a gifted student, for further progress in training, development and education.

Conclusion

The conducted research, which was based on the methodology of the planned mutually conditioned pedagogical co-creation of teachers with students in an innovative educational environment, served as the basis for innovative educational activities of teachers in the system of teaching gifted youth, which led to positive results.

It is revealed that when developing creative abilities of gifted students, in search of the most appropriate methods of teaching and upbringing, a successful teacher working in an innovative school is involved in co-creation of "himself" or "herself", understanding and giving "himself" or "herself" an account from three positions: the past, analyzing work experience; the present, evaluating the results of today's work; the future, making a forecast of designing his professional (personal) roadmap and the trajectory of professional development of gifted youth.

It is proved, on the one hand, that a teacher who has pedagogical giftedness, participates in innovative educational activities, has multifunctional personal qualities for continuous work in the system of teaching gifted youth, on the other hand, participates in creative activities to improve the personality of his students, precedes the development of new areas of intellectual giftedness among young people, thanks to mutually conditioned pedagogical co-creation, which leads to the planned mutually conditioned results.

The author's contribution to the study is determined by the fact that the authors personally participated in innovative educational activities, which are the result of working with gifted students, interacting at all stages of the experimental study.

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